

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AYURVEDA360

**AYURVEDA
360**

**PEER-REVIEWED
BIMONTHLY JOURNAL**

| www.ayurveda360.in/journal

ISSN

PRINT:

3048-7382

ONLINE:

3048-7390

2025

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 5

MARCH-

APRIL

COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

Access this article online

Scan Here

Website:

www.ayurveda360.in/journal

ISSN

PRINT: 3048-7382

ONLINE: 3048-7390

Bimonthly Journal

Publication History:

Submitted: 11-February-2025

Revised: 14-March-2025

Accepted: 02-April-2025

Published: 15-April-2025

How to cite this article:

K. Sharma, M. Vaidya, S. Kumar, & R. Rai (2025). *Analytical Evaluation And Quality Control Parameters For Lipid Based Ayurvedic Formulations: A Comprehensive Review*, 1(5), 314–334. <https://doi.org/10.63247/3048-7390.vol.1.issue5.6>

Analytical Evaluation And Quality Control Parameters For Lipid Based Ayurvedic Formulations: A Comprehensive Review

Dr. Karunanidhi Sharma * Dr. Meghna Vaidya ** Dr. Sanjay Kumar *** Dr. Rajeev Rai ****

*Department of Rasashastra & Bhaishajya Kalpana, National Institute of Ayurveda, Jaipur,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2523-1713>

** Department of Rasashastra & Bhaishajya Kalpana, Mahatma Jyotiba Fule Ayurveda Medical

College, Jaipur, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4193-1269>

*** Department of Rasashastra & Bhaishajya Kalpana, National Institute of Ayurveda, Jaipur,

**** Department of R&D Healthcare, Emami Ltd., Kolkata, West Bengal, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0298-6198>

Abstract

Introduction:

In Ayurveda, oil and fat-based formulations, known as Sneha Kalpana, are extensively used for treating various ailments. These formulations often face quality degradation due to oxidation, leading to unpleasant odors and health risks. Therefore, establishing robust quality control parameters is crucial to ensure the safety, efficacy, and consistency of these formulations. This review focuses on the analytical techniques and tests employed for quality control of Ayurvedic lipid-based formulations.

Methods:

The review compiles and discusses various physical, chemical, and contaminant-related quality control parameters used to evaluate oil and fat-based Ayurvedic formulations. Methods such as refractive index measurement, congealing point, iodine value, acid value, peroxide value, saponification value, and fatty acid composition analysis are reviewed. Additionally, tests for contaminants like heavy metals, aflatoxins, and pesticide residues are covered. Analytical techniques, including HPTLC, HPLC,

GC, and gas-liquid chromatography, are also explored for identifying and quantifying active compounds.

Results:

The review summarizes various tests critical for maintaining the quality of Ayurvedic oils and fats, such as the Baudouin test for sesame oil and the Polybromide test for mustard oil. It provides insights into the effects of oxidation on lipid-based formulations, including changes in fatty acid composition and the formation of secondary oxidation products, which affect product quality. The study also highlights the significance of analyzing contaminants and the importance of compliance with regulatory standards.

Discussion:

The study emphasizes the necessity of implementing rigorous quality control measures in the production of Ayurvedic oil-based formulations to ensure product consistency and safety. By adopting modern analytical techniques and expanding chemical parameters, the standardization of these formulations can be achieved. The integration of new quality control measures, including tests for secondary oxidation and active compounds, will contribute to improving the safety, efficacy, and global acceptance of Ayurvedic products.

Keywords- Sneha Kalpana, Ayurvedic medicine, Quality control, Sneha Paka, Tila Taila

Address for Correspondence:

Dr. Karunanidhi Sharma, Department of Rasashastra & Bhaishajya Kalpana, National Institute of Ayurveda, Jorawar Singh Gate, Amer Road, Jaipur-302002

Email ID: karunanidhisharma376@gmail.com

Licensing and Distribution

	This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License . (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) You are free to share, copy, redistribute, remix, transform, and build upon this work for any purpose, even commercially, provided that appropriate credit is given to the original author(s) and source, a link to the license is provided, and any changes made are indicated.
---	--

Publisher Information

This journal is published under the tradename **Ayurveda360**, which is registered under UDYAM-KR-27-0044910.

Introduction

Ayurveda, known as the "science of life," encompasses a diverse range of ingredients and practices within the traditional Indian system of medicine. These ingredients include botanicals, metals, minerals, animal products, gemstones, organic and non-organic poisons, and calcium compounds. Through specific pharmaceutical processes, these ingredients are transformed into various dosage forms, including liquid forms, solid forms, and semi-solid forms.[1] Among the wide array of Ayurvedic dosage forms, oil and fat-based formulations (Sneha Kalpana) hold significant importance. These formulations involve the processing of herbal juices, decoctions, and pastes with oils or fats. They are administered both internally and externally to address specific disease conditions, following precise dosing protocols.[2]

Fats and oils, key components of these formulations, consist of glycerol esters and fatty acids. While pure fats are colorless, odorless, and tasteless, lipid-soluble substances enhance their sensory properties. However, they are prone to oxidation, leading to rancidity and potential health risks. Factors like fatty acid

composition, processing, heat, light, water content, metals, and antioxidants influence oxidation.[3] In Ayurveda, fats and oils are heated with herbs and liquids, stored long-term, and consumed. Quality control before, during, and after processing is essential to ensure safety, efficacy, and high standards.

In this comprehensive review, we aim to explore the quality control parameters applicable to fats and oil-based formulations in Ayurveda. We shed light on their significance and rationale for application in these products. By examining analytical evaluation and control parameters, we provide insights into the critical aspects of ensuring quality standards in Ayurvedic oils and lipid-based formulations.

Oil and Fat-based Formulations in Ayurveda (Sneha Kalpana)

Sneha Kalpana, a vital dosage form in Ayurveda, involves the processing of oils or fats with herbs. It can be subdivided into four distinct phases for a clearer understanding. The first phase is Kalka, where specific herbs are transformed into a paste. The second phase is Sneha, which incorporates oil or fat, or sometimes both. The third phase is Drava, involving the addition of liquid

media such as juices, herbal decoctions, infusions, milk, curd, gruel water, buttermilk, meat soup, or water. The fourth phase is Gandha, which includes fragrant substances like saffron, camphor, clove, cinnamon bark and leaves, cardamom, vetiver, leaves of specified plants as indicated in the text. Phases I, II, and III are combined in specific proportions (generally 1:4:16 for Phase I:II:III) and heated over mild to moderate heat until specific process completion characteristics are achieved. The mixture is then filtered, and if fragrancin is required, it is performed on the filtered oil/fat. After another round of filtration, the formulation is ready for use. [2]

Sneha Kalpana formulations provide a versatile approach to treating various ailments, used both externally and internally via oral intake, Basti (medicated enema), Nasya (nasal application), and massage. These time-tested Ayurvedic preparations are renowned for their efficacy in enhancing health and well-being.

Lipids used in Ayurveda as base in Sneha Kalpana:

Ayurveda utilizes various oils and fats from both vegetable and animal sources. These include sesame

oil, castor oil, coconut oil, mustard oil, linseed oil, Karanja oil, radish oil, Indian beech oil, drumstick oil, walnut oil, pistachio oil, bael oil, and black mustard oil, as mentioned in the text. In terms of fats, ghee, butter, clarified butter, animal fats, milk fat, curd fat, muscle fats, and bone marrows are indicated and used. Among these, sesame oil is highly regarded, while ghee is considered the best among all fats and oils.[4] In practice, sesame oil, ghee, coconut oil, and mustard oil are the most commonly used.

Quality assessment and control parameters for Lipids and Sneha formulations:

A. Identity and purity test-

Quality assessment of fats and oils starts with identification and purity tests, which include detailed descriptions of their organoleptic features like color, odor, appearance, feel, clarity, and identity. Specific tests are performed to verify the identity and purity. Comprehensive summary of these tests, serving to confirm oil identity and detect any potential adulteration are given below:

- 1. Baudouin test (test for sesame oil)-** It detects sesame oil based on the reaction between phenols and furfurals in an acidic solution. [5] A pink or red color in the acid layer confirms sesame oil presence. [6]

2. Polybromide test for Mustard oil-

Identifies fatty acids with three or more non-conjugated double bonds using bromine. The formation of a precipitate confirms their presence, making it more reliable for fatty acid detection than glycerides.[7]

3. Argemone oil test- Mustard oil is often adulterated with argemone oil. It is detected via TLC/HPTLC. Alkaloids (sanguinarine and dihydrosanguinarine) fluoresce yellow-orange under UV light, confirming contamination.[8]

4. Test for castor oil- The method detects the presence of triricinolein, the main triglyceride component of castor oil, using TLC/HPTLC. The presence of castor oil appears as a distinct spot at an Rf value of ~0.25.[9]

5. Test for presence of palm oil [Palmolein]- Palm oil is very commonly used for adulteration in many vegetable oils. This test Uses the cloud point method, where palmolein crystallizes at ~10°C. Gradual cooling and stirring determine the temperature at which cloudiness appears, indicating palm oil presence.[10]

6. Test for presence oil animal fat- To detect animal fat, fat crystals should be examined microscopically. Animal fats like beef tallow and lard have unique crystalline structures visible under a microscope. Fat samples are dissolved,

recrystallized, and observed under a microscope.[11]

7. Mineral oil test- Mineral oil is a mixture of colorless, odorless, and light alkanes derived from petroleum. Its presence in edible oils is undesirable as it can contaminate the oils and impact their quality and safety for consumption. The test Uses Holde's Test (turbidity formation in hot water) and TLC/HPTLC (faster spot movement due to non-polarity) to detect mineral oil adulteration in edible oils. [12,13]

8. Cotton seed oil test- Based on the reaction of cyclopropenoid fatty acids with sulfur in carbon disulfide, producing a red color, confirming the presence of cottonseed oil. [14]

B. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS:

1. Refractive index

The refractive index [RI] measures light bending when passing between substances. While typically determined relative to air rather than vacuum, RI is characteristic for each oil type and influenced by factors like unsaturation, oxidation, and heat treatment. RI increases with oxidation and unsaturation levels. [15,16] Typically measured using Abbe's refractometer with sodium light's D-line ($\lambda = 589.3 \text{ nm}$) as the reference.[17]

2. Wt per ml & Specific gravity

The mass per unit volume of fats and oils is measured to convert volume to mass or vice versa. It requires measuring the mass of a certain volume at a specified temperature using a calibrated pycnometer/RD bottle. This parameter is applicable to fats and oils which does not deposit crystals at determination temperature. Mass per unit volume is expressed in g/ml or Kg/L and is similar to specific gravity. Specific gravity is determined at fixed temperatures [25 °C and 60 °C], while mass per unit volume allows flexibility in temperature selection [25, 40, 50 or 60°C, and if required higher temperature]. API recommends conducting both tests at 25 °C, while AOCS provides different methods.[18-20] The composition, saturation levels, oxidation, and polymerization of fats can affect their mass per unit volume, especially when processed with herbs. [21,22]

3. Congealing point

Congealing point is the temperature at which a fat solidifies, indicating its resistance to flow. It applies to fats and oils that solidify within the temperature range of 24-45°C, based on their triglyceride composition. It is an important indicator of purity and is determined by the mixture of the liquid and solid phases.[23] Titer point

is a similar test specific to fatty acid mixtures from saponified fat or oil samples, reflecting their compositions.[24] Congealing point is unique to different fats and plays a role in determining storage conditions.

4. Smoke point determination

The smoke point, also known as the burning point, is the temperature at which oil produces bluish smoke under specific conditions.[25] Factors like oil volume, container size, air currents, light source, and FFA content affect the smoke point. Higher FFA leads to lower smoke points, but FFA alone is an unreliable indicator of heat resistance.[26,27] Determining the smoke point involves gradually heating the oil and observing continuous bluish smoke.[35] Sesame oil, with a smoke point of around 180°C, is favored in Ayurvedic cooking and formulations. Its favorable characteristics make it suitable for heating and cooking in Ayurvedic Sneha Paka preparations.[21]

5. Flash point determination

The flash point is the lowest temperature at which a liquid can produce an ignitable mixture in the air near its surface. It is determined by applying a test flame to the sample under specific conditions. The sample

is heated slowly with stirring, and a small test flame is introduced at intervals until the vapor above the sample ignites momentarily. The Pensky Marten [closed cup] method is commonly used for flash point testing.[28] It is essential for assessing the suitability and safety of oils during handling, transport, and processing. Determining the flash point enables informed decisions, ensuring product quality, and preventing accidents and fires.[29]

6. Optical rotation

The optical rotation test Evaluates fat and oil purity by measuring light rotation due to chiral compounds. Using a polarimeter with a sodium lamp, samples dissolved in chloroform are analyzed to detect changes in color, concentration, and processing effects.[30]

7. Viscosity

Viscosity greatly influences fats and oils, impacting flow and functionality across various uses. The Brookfield viscometer, a common tool, gauges viscosity through torque on a rotating spindle within the sample. Analyzing torque and calibrating with reference fluids reveals viscosity. Temperature, shear rate, and preparation influence it, demanding controlled conditions. Reference values assess results,

affirming fats and oils' quality and suitability for distinct applications.[31]

8. Determination of color

Color measurement is pivotal in the oils and fats industry, assessing color preferences during refining and processing like heating, cooking, and infusion. This involves comparing oils with Lovibond glasses. Color is determined using red and yellow slides in a specified cell. A glass cell is filled, placed in the tintometer, and color adjusted until a match occurs. This technique ensures accurate color evaluation, aiding quality control and desired visual traits for various applications.[32]

C. CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND PARAMETERS:

1. Saponification Value

Saponification is the process of converting fat or oil into soap and alcohol through the action of aqueous alkali. The saponification value [SV] provides insights into the properties of the oils involved. A higher SV indicates a lower average length of fatty acids, a lighter mean molecular weight of triglycerides, and vice versa. SV is determined by measuring the amount of alkali required to saponify a specific quantity of the test sample. This is expressed as the number of mg

of potassium hydroxide [KOH] needed to neutralize the fatty acids resulting from the complete hydrolysis of the sample. [33] As time passes, the fatty acids undergo decomposition, resulting in a shorter average length and higher SV for oils. An increasing SV suggests oil deterioration.[34].

2. Unsaponified matter

Unsaponified matter refers to substances that remain soluble in fats and oils after saponification, are insoluble in water, but can be dissolved in test solvents like Light Petroleum or diethyl ether. These substances include natural lipids such as sterols, aliphatic alcohols, pigments, vitamins, hydrocarbons, and non-volatile foreign organic matter at 100°C. Diethyl ether is commonly used as a solvent to determine unsaponified matter.

In Ayurveda, herbs are cooked with oils, and their active components dissolve in the oils. Analyzing unsaponified matter helps understand herb solubility. The process involves saponifying the sample with alkali [KOH] and dissolving it in organic solvents like ether or hexane as per recommended standards.[32,33] Determining unsaponified matter provides valuable insights into the composition and properties of oils and

fats, aiding their application in Ayurvedic preparations and other fields.

3. Iodine value

The iodine value [IV] measures unsaturation in fats and oils by counting double bonds in triglycerides. It indicates melting point and oxidative stability linked to unsaturation. Higher IV means more unsaturation and higher oxidation susceptibility, while lower IV suggests oxidation of unsaturated bonds in fatty acids.[15,34-36] To determine IV, iodine uptake is measured per 100 parts of the sample. Iodometry involves adding an iodine solution, and groups like $-C=C-$ bonds react, reducing the color strength. The required iodine amount maintains the yellow/brown color, revealing iodine-sensitive groups.[37] Methods include monochloride, pyridine bromide (API), and cyclohexane acetic acid (AOCS) which ensure accurate assessment of unsaturation, aiding quality evaluation and determining oxidative stability in fats and oils.[37,38]

4. Acid Value (AV)/ Free fatty acid (FFA)

Free fatty acids (FFA) or acid value (AV) are key indicators of lipid quality, affecting sensory and physicochemical properties. Higher

AV suggests extensive hydrolysis, often caused by lipase activity, high temperatures, hydrolysis, and oxidation. FFA speeds up hydroperoxide decomposition, leading to secondary oxidation and unpleasant tastes.[39] Titrimetric and potentiometric methods are used to used acidity in such samples (ISO). [40] AV represents the amount of potassium hydroxide [KOH] needed to neutralize free acids per g of the sample.[41]

Measuring free fatty acids is crucial for assessing Ayurvedic oil and fat quality. It evaluates hydrolysis and lipid degradation in traditional formulations. Monitoring FFA levels ensures freshness, potency, and therapeutic properties. Controlling acidity maintains sensory characteristics and prevents rancidity.

5. Peroxide value

The peroxide value [PV] measures the initial oxidation and rancidity in fats and oils. It indicates the presence of peroxide and hydroperoxide compounds formed during primary oxidation. PV is expressed as milliequivalents [meq] of active oxygen per 1000 g of substance. The iodometric titration methods are used for determination of PV.[30,42] PV is commonly used as a chemical method

to assess the oxidative deterioration of oils. This test provides insights into the extent of the initial oxidation stage and the development of flavor associated with the oxidation of fats and oils. It is applicable for peroxide values ranging from 0 to 30 meq of active oxygen per kg. This method is used to determine the primary oxidation of such samples

6. Water content

The presence of water content in fats and oils can be very critical. In the Ayurvedic Sneha Paka processing oils/Ghee are processed with herbal juice, decoction, milk, or water. Water content in the final product (Siddha Sneha) decides the process completion and quality of the product as well.[43] Water acts as a barrier against the reaction of fatty acids and oxygen when present in higher quantities. However, when the water content is reduced, oxidation of fats and oils occurs at a faster rate, inducing the hydrolysis of ester bonds and making oxygen more effective results in the formation of various fatty acids and their undesirable breakdown products, leading to off-flavors.[44,45]

Checking water content in Ayurvedic oils and ghee is vital. Karl Fischer titration is commonly used for this purpose. The allowable moisture limit

in edible oils is usually below 0.2% w/w.[46] Strict control of water content ensures stability, shelf life, and quality of Ayurvedic preparations, preventing rancidity.

7. Para anisidine value

The p-anisidine value is a key parameter for assessing secondary oxidation in oils and fats. It measures the oxidation history, mainly involving aldehydes and ketones. The reaction with para anisidine produces a measurable product at 350 nm. This test is applicable to both volatile and non-volatile oils and is particularly sensitive to unsaturated volatile aldehydes compared to saturated volatile aldehydes. Therefore, it serves as a reliable method for assessing secondary oxidation products.[47] By analyzing this value, the extent of secondary oxidation and the potential development of off-flavors and odors can be determined, aiding in quality control and shelf life assessment.

8. Totox value

Totox is the total oxidation value, calculated by adding the p-anisidine value to twice the peroxide value. It provides an overall assessment of the deterioration and oxidation in fats and oils. A lower Totox value indicates higher oil quality.[48]

9. Thiobarbituric acid reactive substances [TBARS]

TBARS are byproducts of fat and oil oxidation. The TBARS assay detects lipid oxidation by measuring malondialdehyde [MDA], a breakdown product of unsaturated fatty acids. In this assay, TBA reacts with MDA, forming a red-colored product measured at 532-535 nm. The TBARS number represents MDA content in mg per kg. However, not all lipid oxidation generates MDA, which can affect TBARS data accuracy.[49] Spectrophotometric methods are employed in the TBARS assay to assess lipid oxidation, providing valuable information on quality, stability, and shelf life of fats and oils.[50]

10. Sterol and cholesterol compositions

Analyzing sterol and cholesterol composition in fats and oils is crucial for assessing their quality and authenticity. Gas chromatography (GC) accurately separates and quantifies sterols, while reversed-phase HPLC is used for cholesterol analysis.[51,52] The determination of total sterol and cholesterol content provides valuable insights into the nutritional value, potential health benefits, and possible adulteration of the fat or oil sample.

11. Total ester value

Total ester value is a critical parameter for measuring esterified fatty acids in oils and fats. Esters are common lipids formed from the reaction between an alcohol and an acid. It reflects the degree of esterification, which affects product quality and stability. Calculated as the difference between saponification value and acid value, higher ester values indicate greater ester content and lower molecular weight fatty acids.[53] Determining the total ester value involves lipid extraction, ester hydrolysis, and titration with a standardized base like NaOH.[54] This process helps assess purity, authenticity, and shelf life, with higher esterification levels indicating reduced susceptibility to oxidation and rancidity.

12. Rancidity test

Rancidity refers to the unpleasant odor and taste that develops in edible fats and oils due to oxidative or hydrolytic degradation. As stored oils age, they can undergo oxidation and become rancid, with aldehydes contributing to the rancid flavor. The Kries test and UV absorption measurements are commonly used to assess rancidity.[55-56]. UV absorption measurements detect the presence of oxidized fatty acids with conjugated

double bonds, with different absorption peaks for dienes and trienes. UV absorption is useful for comparing relative changes in oil oxidation but not for quantifying the extent of oxidation.[57]

13. Hexaneal Tests

Hexaneal tests, also known as hexane value tests, are employed to quantify the hexane-soluble material content in fats and oils. Hexane serves as a solvent during lipid extraction from edible fats and oils, and the hexaneal test gauges the solubility of lipids in hexane. This test is widely utilized to evaluate the quality and purity of fats and oils, as well as to detect impurities or contaminants. In the context of Ayurvedic oils and Ghee, the hexaneal test aids in determining the portion of drugs dissolved in oils, distinct from non-lipid components.[58]

14. Differential Scanning Calorimetry [DSC]

Differential Scanning Calorimetry [DSC] analyzes thermal properties and predicts oxidative stability and shelf life of fats and oils. By detecting heat flow during controlled temperature changes, DSC assesses an oil's susceptibility to oxidation, aiding in quality evaluation and selection of oils with better stability.[59] DSC also helps determine the shelf life of oils,

informing storage and packaging strategies.[60]

15. Determination of presence of unsaturated Fatty acid in Oil and Fats [Bellier test]

The Bellier test is a qualitative method used to detect unsaturated fatty acids in fats and oils. This test relies on the observation of insoluble precipitates formed when unsaturated fatty acids react with specific chemicals. Each oil has its unique precipitation temperature for oils containing long-chain saturated fatty acids.[61]

16. Rancimat test/Oxidative stability index

The Rancimat test measures the oxidative stability of fats and oils by determining the induction time for volatile oxidation products to form. It relies on changes in conductivity caused by volatile organic acids. This test is important for assessing shelf life and quality, as longer induction times indicate greater resistance to oxidation.[62]

In the Rancimat test, airflow is passed through a fat or oil sample at a constant temperature [50-220 °C], causing oxidation and the formation of volatile compounds. These compounds, including formic acid, are carried by the airflow and absorbed into a measuring solution [distilled water], where conductivity is

monitored. A significant increase in conductivity signals the end of the induction period, indicating the stability of fats and oils against oxidation. Longer induction times suggest greater resistance to oxidative processes, which is important for assessing shelf life, quality, and suitability for different applications and storage conditions.[63] The Rancimat method offers efficient analysis of oils and fats, correlating with sensory and analytical methods, ensuring the production of stable and high-quality lipid-based products.

D. COMPOSITIONS AND CONSTITUENTS:

1. Fatty acid composition

The fatty acid composition of fats and oils plays a significant role in their nutritional and functional properties. analyzed by converting fatty acids into methyl esters via esterification (using boron trifluoride or methanol-alkali). Gas-liquid chromatography (GLC) with a flame ionization detector (FID) separates and quantifies them. Comparing elution patterns with standards identifies fatty acids.[64,65] Alternative esterification methods suit neutral oils (acid value <2), providing an effective means to determine fatty acid profiles and understand composition changes caused by

processing, heating, cooking, or the addition of other ingredients.[66]

2. Determination of total polar compounds:

The determination of total polar compounds is crucial for assessing the degradation of fats and oils during heating, cooking, or frying. These processes can lead to the formation of polar components, including monoglycerides, diglycerides, and free fatty acids. Polar compounds in fats and oils, both unused and processed, are analyzed using silica gel column chromatography. Polar components elute first, followed by non-polar ones. Further analysis via UV-Vis spectrophotometry or gas chromatography determines their properties.[67]

The polar fraction of Ayurvedic oils and fats may contain the active biological ingredients. Assessing the polar components is crucial for evaluating quality, determining active ingredient concentration, and gaining insights into the formulation and effectiveness of Ayurvedic products.

3. Oil Soluble extractive value

Lohakar et al. devised a method to determine the oil soluble extractive value of processed herbs in Sesame oil using a 90% v/v aqueous methanol solvent. They found that this solvent

was effective in extracting the desired components. The procedure involved adding 100 ml of 90% v/v aqueous methanol to 50 ml of the medicated oil in a conical flask, stirring it for an hour with a magnetic stirrer, and then storing the mixture in a deep freezer at -20°C for 2 days to solidify the oils. The top methanol layer was filtered, yielding the methanol extract for further experiments, including extractive value calculation and TLC profiling. This method provides a reliable approach for extracting the oil soluble components of herbs within Sesame oil, facilitating subsequent analysis and evaluation.[68]

4. Fingerprinting through TLC/HPTLC

Fingerprinting Ayurvedic oils and fat-based products using TLC and HPTLC is crucial for ensuring quality and authenticity. TLC separates and identifies compounds in complex mixtures, providing specific fingerprints for different oils and fats. HPTLC offers improved resolution and sensitivity, making it useful for analyzing minor components and impurities. These fingerprinting techniques play a vital role in authenticating Ayurvedic oils and fat-based products, detecting adulteration, identifying specific botanical ingredients, and assessing overall

product quality. The generated fingerprints serve as reference standards for quality control and aid in the development of standardized formulations.[69]

5. Active compounds identification and quantification

Identification and quantification of active compounds in Ayurvedic oils and ghee-based products are vital for quality and efficacy. HPTLC, HPLC, and GC are employed for this purpose. HPTLC separates and visualizes polyphenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids. HPLC quantifies markers like curcumin and boswellic acids. GC analyzes volatile compounds such as essential oils and fatty acids in ghee. These techniques ensure consistency and potency, contributing to quality control and formulation. By standardizing the identification and quantification of active compounds, these methods contribute to quality control, formulation, authentication, and therapeutic effectiveness of Ayurvedic oils and ghee-based products.[65,69]

E. CONTAMINANTS:

In addition to other tests, the analysis of heavy metals is conducted to detect potential contamination that may arise during the production, processing, packaging, and storage of these

products. Heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and arsenic have the potential to contaminate fats and oils, and their consumption in high concentrations can lead to health risks, including long-term accumulation in the body and adverse effects on human health. These heavy metals are also known to catalyze and accelerate the oxidation process of oils and fats. Furthermore, the presence of water along with heavy metals can significantly hasten the oxidation process,[70] which is particularly relevant in Ayurvedic oils and fats, as certain oils undergo processing with arsenic and lead compounds.[71] Therefore, heavy metal analysis becomes a crucial parameter in conjunction with other quality parameters for ensuring product safety. The analysis typically involves sample preparation followed by instrumental techniques such as atomic absorption spectroscopy [AAS], inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry [ICP-MS] for quantifying the specific heavy metals present in the formulation[72].

The presence of contaminants like aflatoxins and pesticide residues is a concern in vegetable-based oils. Aflatoxins, specifically types B1, B2, G1, and G2, are commonly analyzed

using HPTLC and Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay [ELISA].[73] Pesticide residue testing includes various types such as organochlorine, organophosphorus, carbamate, pyrethroid, and herbicides, with limits set by different countries.[74] Gas chromatography [GC] is typically employed for this analysis.[75] Microbial load testing ensures fats and oils' safety by detecting bacteria, yeast, and mold. Total viable count (TVC) measures overall microbes, while specific tests identify pathogens or spoilage organisms. Ensuring the absence or controlled levels of these contaminants is essential for maintaining the quality and safety of vegetable-based oils.[76]

Discussion

Quality control plays a vital role in ensuring the safety and effectiveness of pharmaceutical products. The standardization of quality control parameters is essential for producing safe and effective pharmaceuticals consistently. Various techniques are employed to assess and control the quality of raw materials, during the manufacturing process, and in finished products. These techniques can be regulated to establish the necessary quality standards. In the context of oils and fats, which comprise

triglycerides formed by esterifying glycerol with fatty acids, maintaining quality is influenced by various factors such as saturation levels, time, temperature, storage conditions, light exposure, water content, and the presence of heavy metals. During the initial stages of oxidation, unsaturated fatty acids react with oxygen, resulting in the formation of primary oxidation products such as hydroperoxides and free fatty acids. Hydroperoxides, being highly reactive, undergo further chemical reactions leading to the generation of secondary oxidation products, including aldehydes and ketones. These secondary oxidation products are responsible for the rancid odor associated with deteriorated oils and fats. [77]

To determine the quality of raw and processed lipids, several physical and chemical characteristics can be employed. Developing standardized methods through scientific processes is essential for assessing and ensuring the quality of these lipids. The Government of India has established standards for various lipid formulations such as Ghee, sesame oil, mustard oil, castor oil, and specific preparations like Changeri Ghrita, Mahakalyanaka Ghrita, Chandanadi Taila, Jatyadi Taila, and

Narayan Tail through BIS and API.[78,74] These standards primarily focus on physical and chemical parameters. However, it is crucial to expand these parameters to include tests like p-anisidine value, rancimat test, TBRAS, and others to assess secondary oxidation. Additionally, adopting a marker-based approach for both raw materials and finished products, along with establishing standardized fingerprints for all prepared formulations, will further enhance the standardization of product quality.

While some progress has been made in developing fingerprints for formulations like Shadbindu Taila, Anu Taila, Kalyanaka Ghrita, and Dhatriyadi Ghrita,[75,76,79,80] it is imperative to implement these parameters in manufacturing practices to consistently deliver safe and effective products. Moreover, there is a need to explore the area of oil/fat soluble extractive values in Ayurveda Sneha paka, which refers to the amount of active compound transferred from the raw material to

the final product and the extent to which the active component undergoes modification. Limited research has been conducted in this direction, making it an open field for further exploration. Understanding these values will contribute to comprehending the mechanism of action of Ayurvedic drugs under different conditions. Analytical techniques, such as chromatography, spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry, are commonly employed for quality assessment. Stability testing is also crucial to determine shelf life and storage conditions.

Conclusion:

Quality control in Ayurvedic medicine ensures safety, efficacy, and consistency. Expanding chemical parameters, adopting marker-based approaches, and integrating modern analytical techniques enhance standardization. Compliance with regulations and stability testing further improve quality, promoting wider acceptance of Ayurveda.

Conflict of interest- Nil

References

1. Savrikar S, Ravishankar B. Bhaishajya Kalpanaa - The Ayurvedic Pharmaceutics - An Overview. *Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med.* 2010 Apr 3;7[3]:174–84.
2. Vidyasagar PS. 9th Chapter, Sneha Paribhasha. In: Sharandhara Samhita of Shree Sharangadharacharya with the commentaries Adhamalla's Diika and Kashirama's Gudhartha dipika. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2013. p. 212–32.
3. National Research Council (US) Committee on Diet and Health. *Diet and Health: Implications for Reducing Chronic Disease Risk.* Washington (DC):

- National Academies Press (US); 1989. 7, Fats and Other Lipids. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK218759/>.
4. Sastri K, Chaturvedi G. Verse No. 11-13, Chapter 13- Sneha Adhyaya, Surta Sthana. In: Vidyotini Hindi commentary on Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy; 2009. p. 256-7.
 5. A simplified Baudouin test for the detection of adulteration of butter and ghee with vanaspati. *J Inst Chem India*. 1959 Jan 1;31[4]:177–9.
 6. Anonyms. Test for presence of Sesame Oil [Baudouin Test]. In: Manual of methods analysis of Foods: Oils and Fats. New Delhi: Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India.; 2015. p. 39-40. [Lab Manual 2].
 7. Cocks VL, Rede CV. Laboratory Handbook for Oil and Fats Analysis. London: Academic Press; 1966. 147–148 p.
 8. Anonymous. Test for presence of Argemone oil. In: Manual methods of Analysis for Adulterants and Contaminates in Foods. New Delhi: Indian Council of Medical Research, Govt. of India.; 1990. p. 12.
 9. Anonymous. Modified test for presence of Castor oil. In: ISI Handbook of Food Analysis: Part XIII. New Delhi: Indian Standards Institution; 1984. p. 91.
 10. Anonymous. Determination of Cloud Point in Palmolein [and test for presence of palmolein in other oils]. In: Manual of methods analysis of Foods: Oils and Fats. New Delhi: Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India.; 2015. p. 38. [Lab Manual 2].
 11. Anonymous. Test for presence of Animal body fat in vegetable fat [microscopic examination of fat crystals]. In: Manual of methods analysis of Foods: Oils and Fats. New Delhi: Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India.; 2015. p. 49-50. [Lab Manual 2].
 12. Anonymous. Mineral oil test. In: ISI Handbook of Food Analysis-Part XIII. 1984. p. 89.
 13. Anonymous. 3.13. Detection of Mineral Oil [Holde's Test]. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 151.
 14. Anonymous. Test for presence of cottonseed oil. In: Manual of methods analysis of Foods: Oils and Fats. New Delhi: Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India.; 2015. p. 40. [Lab Manual 2].
 15. Gharby S, Harhar H, Bouzoubaa Z, Asdadi A, El Yadini A, Charrouf Z. Chemical characterization and oxidative stability of seeds and oil of sesame grown in Morocco. *J Saudi Soc Agric Sci*. 2017 Apr 1;16[2]:105–11.
 16. Anonymous. Refractive index as an objective method for evaluation of rancidity in edible oils and fats | SpringerLink [Internet]. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF02632705> [cited 2023 Jun 12].
 17. Anonymous. 3.1 Refractive index. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 145.
 18. Anonymous. AOCS Official Method Cc 10c-95 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details?productId=111492>. [cited 2023 Jun 12].
 19. Anonymous. AOCS Surplus Method Cc 10a-25 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details?productId=217949320>. [cited 2023 Jun 12].
 20. Anonymous. 3.2. Weight per Milliliter and Specific Gravity. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 145.
 21. Nduka JKC, Omozuwa PO, Imanah OE. Effect of heating time on the physicochemical properties of selected

- vegetable oils. Arab J Chem. 2021 Apr 1;14[4]:103063.
22. Nancy Idun-Acquah, George Y. Obeng, Ebenezer Mensah, Repetitive Use of Vegetable Cooking Oil and Effects on Physico-Chemical Properties – Case of Frying with Redfish (*Lutjanus fulgens*), *Science and Technology*, Vol. 6 No. 1, 2016, pp. 8-14. doi: 10.5923/j.scit.20160601.02.
23. Anonymous. 3.4.2. Determination of Congealing Range. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 145-147.
24. Jennings, G. W. (1932). Some titer points of mixed fatty acids. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Analytical Edition*, 4(3), 262–263. doi:10.1021/ac50079a007.
25. Anonymous. AOCs Official Method Cc 9a-48 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details?productId=111517> [cited 2023 Jun 13].
26. Gómez-Alonso S, Fregapane G, Salvador MD, Gordon MH. Changes in phenolic composition and antioxidant activity of virgin olive oil during frying. *J Agric Food Chem*. 2003 Jan 29;51[3]:667–72.
27. Thomas, A. (2000). Fats and Fatty Oils. *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*. doi:10.1002/14356007.a10_173
28. Anonymous. Determination of Flash Point: Pensky Martin Closed cup Method. In: *Manual of Methods of Analysis of Food: oils and Fats*. New Delhi: Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India.; 2021. p. 11–2.
29. Hollebhone B. Chapter 4 - Measurement of Oil Physical Properties. Editor(s): Mervin Fingas. *Oil Spill Science and Technology*. Gulf Professional Publishing. 2011. Pages 63-86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-85617-943-0.10004-8>.
30. Anonymous. AOCs Official Method Cd 8b-90 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details/productId/111547>. [cited 2023 Jun 7].
31. Anonymous. ISO 1652 - European Standards [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.en-standard.eu/iso-1652-rubber-latex-determination-of-apparent-viscosity-by-the-brookfield-test-method/>. [cited 2023 Jun 7].
32. Anonymous. Determination of color. In: *Manual of methods of analysis of food Oils*. Food safety and standard authority of India [FSSAI].; 2021. p. 13.
33. Anonymous. Determination of Saponification value. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 149.
34. CB A osanaiye, Gabriel A, Alaje P, Omoniyi A. Effects of different storage temperature on the physicochemical properties of cooking oils available in Nigeria Markets. *European Journal of Academic Essays*. 2015;2[10]:7–14.
35. Zine S, Gharby S, El Hadek M. Physicochemical Characterization of Opuntia ficus-indica Seed Oil from Morocco. *Biosci Biotechnol Res Asia* 2013;10(1)
36. Eromosele IC, Eromosele CO, Innazo P, Njerim P. Studies on some seeds and seed oils. *Bioresour Technol*. 1998 Jun 1;64[3]:245–7.
37. Anonymous. Determination of Iodine value. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 149–50.
38. Anonymous. AOCs Official Method Cd 1d-92 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details?productId=111533>. [cited 2023 Jun 12].
39. Chew SC, Nyam KL. Chapter 6 - Refining of edible oils. In: Galanakis CM, editor. *Lipids and Edible Oils* [Internet]. Academic Press; 2020. p. 213–41. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128171059000069>. [cited 2023 Jun 9].

40. Anonymous. ISO 660:2009. International Organization for Standardization. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/standard/44879.html>. [cited 2023 Jun 9].
41. Anonymous. Determination of Acid value. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India [Part II [Formulations]; vol. IV]. Ghaziabad, UP, India: PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 150.
42. Anonymous. 3.11. Determination of peroxide value. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]; vol. IV]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 150.
43. Vidyasagar PS. Versr No. 12-16. 9th Chapter, Sneha Paribhasha. In: Sharandhara Samhita of Shree Sharangadharacharya with the commentaries Adhamalla's Diika and Kashirama's Gudhartha dipika. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2013. p. 214.
44. Feiner G. Chapter 1 - Meat and Fat. Editor(s): Gerhard Feiner. Salami, Academic Press. 2016. Pages 3-30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809598-0.00001-9>.
45. Zeece M. Chapter Four - Lipids. Introduction to the Chemistry of Food. Academic Press. 2020. Pages 127-161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809434-1.00004-9>.
46. Anonymous. IS 14309 [1995]: Blended Edible Vegetable Oils. [FAD 13: Oils and oil seeds]. New Delhi, Bureau of Indian Standards p.2
47. Irwin JW, Hedges N. 13 - Measuring lipid oxidation. In: Steele R, editor. Understanding and Measuring the Shelf-Life of Food. Woodhead Publishing; 2004. p. 289–316. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9781855737327500172>.
48. Pereira de Abreu DA, Losada PP, Maroto J, Cruz JM. Evaluation of the effectiveness of a new active packaging film containing natural antioxidants [from barley husks] that retard lipid damage in frozen Atlantic salmon [*Salmo salar* L.]. Food Res Int. 2010 Jun 1;43[5]:1277–82.
49. Bai C S, Hardy RW, Hamidoghli A, Chapter 10 - Diet analysis and evaluation. Editor(s): Ronald W. Hardy, Sadasivam J. Kaushik. Fish Nutrition, 4th ed. Academic Press. 2022. Pages 709-743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819587-1.00010-0>.
50. Zeb A, Ullah F. 2016; A simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances in fried fast foods. J Anal Methods Chem. 2016:9412767.
51. Bai G, Ma C, Chen X. Phytosterols in edible oil: Distribution, analysis and variation during processing. Grain Oil Sci Technol. 2021 Mar 1;4[1]:33–44.
52. Anonymous. AOCS Official Method Ch 6-91 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details?productId=114625>. [cited 2023 Jun 13].
53. Belsare GW, Badne SG. Study on physico-chemical characterization of edible oils from agencies of Buldhana district. Int J Res Pharm Chem. 2017;7[4]:525–9.
54. Anonymous. General Chapters: <401> FATS AND FIXED OILS-US Pharmacopeia-ISP 29. Vol. 31(4). P.1157 Available from: http://www.pharmacopeia.cn/v29240/usp_29nf24s0_c401.html. [cited 2023 Jun 12].
55. Roberts PB. IRRADIATION OF FOODS. Applications. In: Caballero B, editor. Encyclopedia of Food Sciences and Nutrition [Second Edition] [Internet]. Oxford: Academic Press; 2003 p. 3386–90. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B012227055X006544>. [cited 2023 Jun 7].
56. Anonymous. 3.15 Rancidity Test [Kreis test]. In: The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations]- Vol. IV]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 151.
57. Anonymous. Determination of Rancidity - UV method. In: Manual of methods analysis of Foods: Oils and Fats. New Delhi: Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, Ministry of Health and

- Family Welfare, Govt. of India.; 2015. p. 95-6. [Lab Manual 2].
58. Anonymous. ISO 663:2017. international Organization for Standardization. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/standard/71269.html> [cited 2023 Jun 8]
59. Anonymous. AOCS Official Method Cj 1-94 [Internet].. Available from: <https://www.aocs.org/attain-lab-services/methods/methods/search-results?method=112540&SSO=True>. [cited 2023 Jun 8]
60. Almoselhy RIM. Applications of Differential Scanning Calorimetry [DSC] in Oils and Fats Research. A Review [Internet]. Rochester, NY; 2020 [cited 2023 Jun 8]. Available from: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3908530>
61. Anonymous. Bellier Test [turbidity temperature] acetic acid method. In: Manual of methods of analysis of food Oils [Internet]. Food safety and standard authority of India [FSSAI]; 2021. p. 32-33. Available from: https://fssai.gov.in/upload/uploadfiles/files/Manual_Revised_Oil_Fats_22_06_2021.pdf
62. García-Moreno PJ, Pérez-Gálvez R, Guadix A, Guadix EM. Influence of the parameters of the Rancimat test on the determination of the oxidative stability index of cod liver oil. *LWT - Food Sci Technol.* 2013 Apr 1;51[1]:303–8.
63. Anonymous. AOCS Official Method Cd 12b-92 [Internet]. Available from: <https://myaccount.aocs.org/PersonifyEbusiness/Store/Product-Details/productId/111524>. [cited 2023 Jun 13].
64. Anonymous. Bureau of Indian Standards - e-Sale Search Result. 2021 [cited 2023 Jun 8]. IS 548: Part Part 3 : Sec 1 : 2021 Methods of Sampling and Test for Oils and Fats Part 3 Advanced Instrumental Methods Section 1 Determination of fatty acid profile. Available from: https://standardsbis.bsbedge.com/BIS_SearchStandard.aspx?Standard_Number=S06V01&id=subdiv
65. Anonymous. Determination of fatty acid composition of oils and fats by gas liquid chromatography: In: : Manual of methods of analysis of food Oils [Internet]. New Delhi: Food safety and standard authority of India [FSSAI].; 2021. p. 44–7. Available from: https://fssai.gov.in/upload/uploadfiles/files/Manual_Revised_Oil_Fats_22_06_2021.pdf
66. Devi A, Khatkar BS. Effects of fatty acids composition and microstructure properties of fats and oils on textural properties of dough and cookie quality. *J Food Sci Technol.* 2018 Jan;55[1]:321–30.
67. Anonymous. Determination of Total polar compounds in edible oils and fats. In: Manual of methods of analysis of food Oils [Internet]. New Delhi: Food safety and standard authority of India [FSSAI]; 2021. p. 114–6. Available from: https://fssai.gov.in/upload/uploadfiles/files/Manual_Revised_Oil_Fats_22_06_2021.pdf
68. Lahorkar P, Ramitha K, Bansal V, Anantha Narayana DB. A comparative evaluation of medicated oils prepared using ayurvedic and modified processes. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2009 Nov;71(6):656-62. doi: 10.4103/0250-474X.59548. PMID: 20376219; PMCID: PMC2846471.
69. Sukumar D, Arimboor R, Arumughan C. HPTLC fingerprinting and quantification of lignans as markers in sesame oil and its polyherbal formulations. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2008 Aug 5;47[4–5]:795–801.
70. Riaz MN, Rokey GJ. Impact of particle size and other ingredients on extruded foods and feeds. In: Riaz MN, Rokey GJ, editors. *Extrusion Problems Solved* [Internet]. Woodhead Publishing; 2012 [cited 2023 Jun 13]. p. 55–63. [Woodhead Publishing Series in Food Science, Technology and Nutrition]. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9781845696641500062>
71. Choudhry P, Rahul. A Review on Kustharakshas Taila. *Int Res J Mod Eng Technol Sci.* March 2023. 5(3). P. 555-9.
72. Anonymous. 2.3.3. Limit Test for Heavy metals. In: *The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations] Vol. IV]*. New Delhi: PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 124. [Part II [Formulations] Vol. IV].
73. Anonymous. 2.6. Test for Aflatoxins. In: *The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-*

- [Part II [Formulations] Vol. IV].. New Delhi: PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017. p. 142. [Part II [Formulations] Vol. IV].
74. Anonymous. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India-[Part II [Formulations] Vol. IV]. New Delhi: PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION FOR INDIAN MEDICINE & HOMOEOPATHY; 2017.
75. Shailajan S, Menon SN, Tiwari BR, Singh AS. Standardization of Shadbindu Taila: An Ayurvedic oil based medicine. *Ayu*. 2013;34[1]:103–7.
76. Diddi S, Lohidasan S, Arulmozhi S, Mahadik KR. Standardization and Ameliorative effect of Kalyanaka ghrita in β -amyloid induced memory impairment in wistar rats. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2023 Jan 10;300:115671.
77. Jerónimo E, Alves SP. Chapter 11 - Lipid-derived oxidation products. In: Lorenzo JM, Munekata PES, Pateiro M, Barba FJ, Domínguez R, editors. *Food Lipids* [Internet]. Academic Press; 2022. p. 231–53. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128233719000149>. [cited 2023 Jun 14].
78. Anonymous. Oils and Oilseeds [FAD 13]—Food and Agriculture Division—Public Safety Standards of India [Internet]. Available from: <https://law.resource.org/pub/in/bis/manifest.fad.13.html>. [cited 2023 Jun 14]
79. Pal RS, Mishra A. Standardization of Dhatriyadi Ghrita: A Herbal Ghee Based Ayurvedic Medicinal Preparation. *Open Med J* [Internet]. 2018 Aug 31;5[1]. Available from: <https://openmedicinejournal.com/VOLUME/5/PAGE/47/FULLTEXT/>. [cited 2023 Jun 14]
80. Meena AK, Rekha P, Perumal A, Ilavarasan R, Singh R, Srikant N, et al. Identification and estimation of bioactive constituents Negundoside, Berberine chloride, and Marmelosin by HPLC and HPTLC for development of quality control protocols for Ayurvedic medicated oil formulation. *Future J Pharm Sci*. 2021;7[1]:171.